

Effect of NaCl on Structural, Spectroscopic and Optical properties of Methyl Orange Doped Urea L-Malic Acid Crystal

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Abstract

Non linear optical single crystals of NaCl and methyl orange doped urea L-malic acid crystals were grown by slow evaporation technique. Good quality single crystals of dimension $10 \times 9 \times 2$ mm³ and $10 \times 9 \times 2$ mm³ are harvested in 20 and 30 days respectively. Influence of dopants in urea L-malic acid was studied. The grown crystals are characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction. The study reveals that the crystal belongs to monoclinic system with P2₁ space group. The structures of the compounds are further confirmed by Fourier Transform Infrared spectra. The effect of optical properties on doping and the transparency of the grown crystals are analyzed by UV-Visible spectra. The micro hardness study shows that the Vickers hardness number of the crystal decreases with increase in applied load. The nonlinear optical test confirms the second harmonic signal generation in the sample.

Keywords: Single Crystal, Slow Evaporation, Monoclinic, Microhardness.

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